

Relationship of Self-Control with Intensity of Tiktok Social Media Use in Universitas Negeri Makassar Studens

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ABSTRACT

Intensity of *tiktok* social media use means that how often individuals access so as to produce a behavior or response. One factor that can affect intensity is self-control. The study was conducted to determine the relationship between self-control and the intensity of *tiktok* social media use in Universitas Negeri Makassar students. This research uses a quantitative approach with person correlation product moment technique. The respondents of study were 381 students of Universitas Negeri Makassar obtained by random sampling. The results showed that there was a negative relationship between self-control and the intensity of *tiktok* social media use in Makassar State University students. This is evidenced by a pearson correlation coefficient of -0,311 and the significance value of 0,000 ($0,000 < 0,05$), so it can be concluded that the hypothesis is accepted. The implication in the research is that understanding is related to the need for students to have self-control so that they can use their time better and for other useful things.

INTRODUCTION

Social media is the new media that is most frequently accessed by people and is used to interact, communicate and work virtually. Social media is popular with young people because communicating with social media is practical, has lots of features, and also seems up to date. There are several social media that are often used by people today. However, the social media that is currently being widely used is Tiktok social media.

Tiktok is a short video sharing application. Tiktok can also be used to broadcast live. Tiktok users can use various features provided by the application, such as interesting and unique filters that can be easily used to create short videos with cool results. Users can also channel their talents by making short videos of dancing, dubbing, and more because they are supported by the music available on the Tiktok application (Michael, 2019). Because of its easy-to-use features, currently Tiktok is popular among all groups, not only children and teenagers but parents also use this application.

Apart from being popular, according to Imron (2018) Tiktok is included in the category of very entertaining applications. Because Tiktok content does not only focus on one content topic but consists of various kinds, such as creative content, entertainment, art, education and also culinary content. Tiktok is also a medium for following trends that can edit videos, images and even audio. Susilowati (2018) stated in her research that the Tiktok application is an application that provides unique and interesting special effects that can be used by users easily so that they can create short videos with cool results and can be shown off to friends or other users.

The Tiktok application is an entertainment medium that follows trends and makes many people like it. Because something that is profitable will create a positive assessment for individuals, even though the Tiktok application has several shortcomings (Demmy, 2018). In line with this opinion, Tiktok has a big influence on life because it is often used as a choice to express emotions and tell what has happened. Not only that, Tiktok is also often used to entertain when you feel bored, stressed, or don't have anything to do.

Demmy (2018), Tiktok has a negative impact, where users seek popularity and unconsciously carry out negative actions. By making videos that are negative, you will quickly get lots of views and shares. Research conducted by Hamed (2017) states that uncontrolled use of social media can cause a person's productivity to decrease. Griffiths (2000) said that when a lot of time is spent doing online activities on social media, a person can lose functional properties and lead to negative consequences

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including addictive behavior and other problems. However, Tiktok also has a positive impact, namely that it can help users express themselves, gain new knowledge and also gain popularity.

Tiktok is something that students use as an escape when they feel bored, stressed and under a lot of pressure. Due to the high enthusiasm and abundance of TikTok content currently, users stay longer accessing it, so they sometimes neglect carrying out their daily activities. The more time spent using social media, the more the intensity of use increases.

Intensity is an activity that is carried out repeatedly. Wulandari (Ardari, 2016) explains that intensity is related to the duration or use of time doing certain activities and the frequency or number of repetitions in a certain time. Juditha (2011) stated that the duration of social media use would be considered normal when use is less than three hours per day and said to be in the high category when it is above three hours per day. If the intensity of use of social media TikTok exceeds normal limits, it will be difficult to control oneself and it will be easier to be exposed to information that can change behavior. Because of this, students must have good self-control to be able to control themselves in controlling the duration of their use of TikTok social media so they do not abuse it.

Averill (Sari, 2014) Self-control is a simple psychological variable that has three different concepts related to the ability to control behavior including three aspects, namely behavior modification, interpretation of unwanted information, and choosing actions based on something that is believed. Self-control is the ability an individual has to reject or change a response, as well as to mediate behavior by refraining from carrying out an undesirable action (Tangney, Baumister, and Boone, 2004).

In line with previous research conducted by Afrelia and Khairat (2022), the higher the intensity of Tiktok use among teenagers, the lower their self-control will be. On the other hand, if the lower the intensity of Tiktok use in teenagers, the higher the self-control they will have. The results of data analysis show a significant negative relationship between the intensity of TikTok use and self-control among teenagers in Nagari Simpang Kapuak District. Mungka District Fifty Cities.

Other research conducted by Kartika Sari Dewi (2015) regarding the relationship between self-control tendencies and the intensity of use of social networks in adolescents shows that there is a weak relationship and leads to negative characteristics between self-control tendencies and the intensity of use of social networks.

Based on the background of the problem and several previous studies described above, it is known that the importance of self-control in students is because there are still many students who lack self-control in using Tiktok social media. This phenomenon is the background for researchers to research "The relationship between self-control and the intensity of use of Tiktok social media in Universitas Negeri Makassar students". The aim of this research is to find out whether there is a relationship between self-control and the intensity of use of social media Tiktok among Makassar State University students.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses a quantitative approach with the Pearson correlation product moment technique which aims to find out whether there is a relationship between the intensity of use of *TikTok* social media and self-control in Universitas Negeri Makassar students. The population in the study were Universitas Negeri Makassar students who used the TikTok application. Participants in this research were 381 students with a sampling technique using random sampling.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

a. Categorization of Intensity of *TikTok* Social Media Use

The *TikTok* social media usage intensity scale consists of 11 items with a score of 1 - 5. The lowest score was 11 and the highest score was 55 ($M = 33$; $SD = 7.333$). The following is the categorization in the table below.

Tabel 1. Percentage of categorization scores on the Intensity of *TikTok* social media use scale

	Intervals	F	%	Criteria
$X < (\mu - \sigma)$	< 25,667	0	0	Low
$(\mu - \sigma) \leq X < (\mu + \sigma)$	25,667 - 40,333	174	45,67	Medium
$X \leq (\mu + \sigma)$	> 40,333	207	54,33	High
Total		381	100	

The data in the table above shows that from data analysis of the intensity of use of TikTok social media variables, it was found that 174 students were in the medium category with a percentage of 45.67%. In the high category, there were 207 students with a percentage of 54.33%. From the data above, it can be concluded that the intensity of the students in this study was in the medium category.

b. Categorization of Self-Control

The TikTok social media usage intensity scale consists of 34 items with a score of 1-5. The lowest score was 34 and the highest score was 170 ($M = 102$; $SD = 22.667$). The following is the categorization in the table below.

Tabel 2. *Percentage of self-control categorization scores*

	Intervals	F	%	Criteria
$X < (\mu - \sigma)$	< 79,333	8	2,1	Low
$(\mu - \sigma) \leq X < (\mu + \sigma)$	79,333 - 124,667	219	57,8	Medium
$X \leq (\mu + \sigma)$	> 124,667	154	40,42	High
Total		381	100	

The data in the table above shows that from the data analysis of the self-control variable, it was found that 8 students were in the low category with a percentage of 2.1%, 219 students were in the medium category with a percentage of 57.48%. In the high category, there were 154 students with a percentage of 40.42%. From the data above, it can be concluded that the intensity of the students in this study was in the medium category.

Assumptions Test

Normality Test

The normality test used in this research is the One Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. According to Siregar (2016), the Kolmogorof-Smirnov test is used to determine the normality of data distribution with samples > 50 .

The normality test results tested using SPSS v.25.0 for Windows are as follows:

Tabel 3. *Normality Test Results*

		Unstandardized Residual
N		381
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	4.00767226
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.042
	Positive	.036
	Negative	-.042
Test Statistic		.042
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.124 ^c

The normality test criteria which can be declared to be normally distributed have a significance level of > 0.05 . Based on the table above, it shows that the significance value is 0.124. This shows that the data is normally distributed in accordance with the normality test decision making.

Linearity Test

Tabel 4. *Linearity Test Results*

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F	Sig.
Between Groups	(Combined)	1170.208	38	30.795	1.884	.002
	Linearity	655.667	1	655.667	40.123	.000
	Deviation from Linearity	514.541	37	13.907	.851	.718

Within Groups	5588.805	342	16.342
Total	6759.013	380	

The linearity test criteria are based on significance which can be stated to be linearly related and has a significance level of > 0.05. Based on the table above, it shows that the significance value is 0.718. This significance value is greater than 0.05, so it can be concluded that there is a linear relationship between self-control and the intensity of use of TikTok social media.

Hypothesis Test

Tabel 5. Hypothesis Test Results

Variable	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (p)	Explanation
Self-Control * Intensity of <i>TikTok</i> Social Media Use	-0,311	0,000	Negatively Correlated

The results of the analysis in the table above show that the correlation coefficient of self-control with the intensity of use of TikTok social media is -0.311 and a significance value of 0.000. If the significance value is smaller than 0.05 then the hypothesis is accepted and conversely if the significance value is greater than 0.05 then the hypothesis is rejected. This means that both variables show a relationship between self-control and the intensity of use of TikTok social media among students in the form of a negative relationship.

The research results show that the significance value of the self-control variable and the intensity of use of social media *TikTok* is 0.000 with a Pearson correlation value of -0.311. The hypothesis criteria are accepted if the significance value is greater than 0.005. So it can be concluded that there is a relationship between self-control and the intensity of use of *TikTok* social media.

The results of this research are in line with previous research conducted by Afrelia and Khairat (2022) regarding the relationship between the intensity of *TikTok* use and self-control in teenagers in Nagari Simpang Kapuak District. Mungka District Fifty Cities. The results of the study show that there is a negative relationship between the intensity of *TikTok* use and self-control in adolescents. This means that the higher the intensity of *TikTok* use, the lower the self-control that teenagers have. Likewise, the lower the intensity of *TikTok* use, the higher the self-control that teenagers have.

Intensity in using *TikTok* social media can be interpreted as how often individuals access it, resulting in behavior or responses (Rahmawati, 2019). Meanwhile, intensity in using *TikTok* social media can be interpreted as how often individuals access it, resulting in behavior or responses. In previous research conducted by Juditha (2011) stated that a person is said to be normal in using social media when the duration of use is one to 3 hours a day with a frequency of use of one to four times a day. When you use *TikTok* social media with an intensity that exceeds normal limits, it can have a negative impact on daily life and it will be difficult to control yourself and it will be easier to be exposed to information that can change behavior.

Based on the percentage of intensity of use of *TikTok* social media, it shows that Universitas Negeri Makassar students have a medium level of intensity of use of *TikTok* social media. The moderate category means that it is quite intense in duration, frequency, attention and appreciation for using *TikTok* social media. This is because there are many interesting features in the *TikTok* application which can attract students to always use the *TikTok* application. Nisa (2019) states that intensity occurs because an activity can give satisfaction or pleasure to someone who does it, so that there can be an increase in intensity because it is always repeated. Derianto & Qorib (2018) assume that the more a person relies on social media for their needs, the more important the role of social media in that person's life becomes.

Meanwhile, the results of data analysis on self-control show that the majority of Universitas Negeri Makassar students have self-control at the medium category level. The medium category can be interpreted as meaning that students have tried and are able to control their behavior, cognition and make decisions in using *TikTok* social media according to their needs. Individuals who have good self-control are individuals who are able to limit the intensity of stimuli, control emotions in certain situations, and are able to manage decisions and assess things subjectively. In line with research conducted by Anggraeni, Praherdhinono and Sultoni (2019) stated that an individual's ability to control themselves and direct their behavior when using the internet can prevent the individual from becoming addicted.

The high intensity of using *TikTok* social media is due to low self-control, meaning that if students are unable to control themselves, high intensity usage of *TikTok* social media will occur. Averill (Sari, 2014) Self-control is a simple psychological variable that has three different concepts related to the ability to control behavior. The psychological concepts in question are the ability to modify behavior, the ability to interpret unwanted information, and finally the ability to choose an action that is believed. Every individual who has good self-control can control themselves, does not get emotional easily, is able to take responsibility and always think positively. Meanwhile, low self-control can occur when individuals are unable to control negative impulses within themselves which can lead to bad behavior without considering the consequences that will occur. In line with previous research conducted by Istri and Asyanti (2017) stated that there is a negative relationship between self-control and internet addiction where individuals who are addicted to the internet are unable to control themselves and may neglect other activities. It can be concluded that there is a negative relationship between self-control and the intensity of use of social media *TikTok* in Universitas Negeri Makassar students. Self-control is really needed so that students can respond and position themselves according to their needs, because too much of anything is not a good thing.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the data analysis that has been carried out, it can be concluded that there is a negative relationship between self-control and the intensity of use of social media *TikTok* in Universitas Negeri Makassar students. Future researchers who want to use the same research theme are expected to search for a lot of information so they can find out what other factors can influence the intensity of use of *TikTok* social media.

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